

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF THE HYGIENIC STATE OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN PERSONS USING COMPLETE REMOVABLE AND REMOVABLE OVERDENTURES SUPPORTED BY IMPLANTS

Jafarov R.,

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine

Head of the Department of Dentistry

Faculty of Medicine, Nakhchivan State University

Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan

Aliyev V.

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine,

Department of Dentistry Faculty of Medicine, teacher

Nakhchivan State University

Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan

Abstract

Dental implantation is a modern method of restoring defects in the dentition and is now increasingly being used in dental practice. Almost all authors, who to some extent touch upon the issues of hygienic care for the oral cavity during implantation, agree that the hygiene of teeth, implants and superstructures has a significant impact on the survival of artificial supports. The presence of fixed and/or removable implant-supported dentures in the oral cavity significantly affects the quality of oral hygiene, as favorable conditions are created for the adhesion of food residues.

After prosthetics, microbial plaque on the crowns and the cervical surface of the implant suprastructure can cause chronic inflammation in the tissues around the implant, which leads to a reduction in the service life of the entire structure. Therefore, all patients with orthopedic constructions require careful individual oral hygiene and prosthesis hygiene.

Keywords: secondary adentia, complete removable lamellar dentures and constructions with push-button fixation.

In recent years, the attention of specialists to the health status and quality of life of older people has increased significantly, due to demographic trends, an increase in life expectancy and, consequently, the number of elderly and senile people in developed countries. [1.2] Thus, despite the successes in modern dentistry it can be expected that for the general population no decrease in the incidence and prevalence of complete edentulous disease is expected, and therefore, an increase in the total number of patients requiring prosthetics for edentulous jaws is expected in the near future.

Traditional removable dentures no longer satisfy elderly and senile patients.[3] They believe that this makes them feel inferior, has a negative impact on their social and psychological status, which significantly reduces the level of quality of life. It is important to understand that more and more older people are working, which leads to an improvement in their economic condition, as well as higher aesthetic and functional requirements for orthopedic construction.[4] Thus, the issues of gerontology in modern dentistry are becoming increasingly important.[5]

In recent years, the indications for dental implantation in persons of older age groups have significantly expanded. [6.7] However, the indications and features of dental prosthetics based on dental implants in the management of elderly and senile patients with complete absence of teeth are still not fully resolved.

The purpose of the study was to compare the level of oral hygiene in patients of older age groups using complete removable lamellar dentures and removable

overdentures in the lower jaw with bar and button fixation on dental implants. We set ourselves the following tasks: 1) to assess the hygienic condition of complete removable laminar dentures in the lower jaw in older patients; 2) to assess the hygienic condition of the overdentures on the lower jaw, based on implants, with a push-button fixation system in older patients; 3) to assess the hygienic condition of mandibular overdentures supported by implants with a beam fixation system in older patients; 4) to compare the level of hygiene of prostheses on the lower jaw of different designs in older patients. Material and methods. We examined 15 patients with complete removable laminar dentures in the lower jaw; 15 patients using removable overdentures in the lower jaw with a bar fixation system, and 15 with button fixation on dental implants. The patients participating in the study ranged in age from 55 to 75 years. All patients are non-smokers. The criteria for not including patients in the study groups was the presence of diseases accompanied by a deterioration in manual skills. Examination of patients was carried out as part of dispensary observation. Before using prostheses, patients were given the following recommendations for caring for structures and the oral cavity: rinse the prosthesis and oral cavity after each meal if necessary; brush with toothpaste the prosthesis from all sides, superstructures in the oral cavity and existing teeth 2 times a day, in the morning and in the evening; when removing the prosthesis at night, leave it in the water. Patients with implant-supported overdentures were advised to use a Philips Sonycare sonic toothbrush. All

patients were divided into 3 groups. Group 1 (n=15) included patients with complete removable lamellar dentures in the lower jaw. The 2nd group (n=15) included patients using mandibular overdentures on dental implants with a push-button fixation system, and the 3rd group (n=15) included patients with a bar fixation system. We evaluated the hygienic condition of the prostheses for the lower jaw of the listed structures. To assess the state of removable dentures in the absence of teeth and justify the effectiveness of preventive measures, we used the hygienic index of removable dentures, which was modified for our study. The essence of this technique is that in order to detect plaque, the inner surfaces of removable dentures in the case of partial absence of teeth are stained with a solution of methylene blue, rinsed with water for 5 s and dried with an air stream for 10 s. The painted prosthesis is conditionally divided into 3 segments: frontal and lateral; the boundaries of which is a line drawn through the middle of the canines on the denture. The assessment of the amount of plaque on the surface of the prosthesis was carried out in each segment under study according to the following criteria: 0 - no staining; 1 - slight staining; 2 — staining less than half of the surface area of the segment; 3 - staining of more than half of the surface area of the segment; 4 — staining of the entire surface of the segment. Then the index value for each prosthesis was evaluated. Interpretation of the results: 0-1.5 - good, 1.5-2.5 - satisfactory, 2.5-4.0 - unsatisfactory level of hygiene. Results. The average assessment of the hygiene of dentures in patients from the 1st group is 1.55, which corresponds to a satisfactory level of hygiene. The average assessment of dental prosthesis hygiene in patients from the 2nd group is 1.58, which corresponds to a satisfactory level of hygiene. The average assessment of dental prosthesis hygiene in patients of the 3rd group is 1.01, which corresponds to a good level of hygiene.

Conclusion.

In the patients of the older age group examined by us, who use complete removable lamellar dentures and removable overdentures on dental implants with push-button fixation, the level of hygiene of removable dentures does not have statistical differences. While the level of hygiene of removable dentures of patients using removable overdentures supported by implants with a bar fixation system has a higher level of hygiene compared to the previous two groups. Thus, patients with

structures with a more complex relief, but at the same time with a smaller area of the plastic base, have a better level of hygiene, which may indicate the awareness of patients with more complex, and therefore more expensive structures, about understanding the importance of the level of hygiene for prolongation lifetime of implants, as well as the effectiveness of additional preventive measures. Also, an important role is played by the smaller volume of the plastic base, which is characteristic of bar structures compared to complete removable lamellar dentures and structures with push-button fixation, since plastic, due to its porosity, is more susceptible to bacterial contamination and accumulation of microbes than metal.

Referenses

1. Kazanskii M.R. Sostoyanie gigeny polosti rta u patsientov raznogo vozrasta s nes"emnymi ortopedicheskimi konstruktsiyami. Dental Forum. 2010; 4: 19-20.
2. Shcherbakova T.A., Zhil'tsova E.S., Vorob'eva M.V. Effektivnyi dopolnitel'nyi predmet gigeny dlya patsientov s ortopedicheskimi konstruktsiyami v polosti rta. Byulleten' meditsinskikh internet-konferentsii. 2017; 7(11): 1615-7.
3. Mikhailenko T.N. Klinicheskaya otsenka sostoyaniya gigeny polosti rta u lits so s"emnymi konstruktsiyami zubnykh protezov na osnovanii integral'nogo indeksa. Meditsinskii vestnik Bashkortostana. 2014; 1. URL:
4. Zholudev S.E., Marenkova M.L. Gigena polosti rta u lits so s"emnymi zubnymi protezami i nekotorye sposoby ee uluchsheniya. Panorama ortopedicheskoi stomatologii. 2005; 3: 36-8.
5. Chesnokov V.A., Efimenko A. V. Otsenka sostoyaniya gigeny polosti rta u lits s metabolicheskim sindromom pri reabilitatsii s"emnymi plastinchnymi protezami. Sovremennyye problemy nauki i obrazovaniya. 2017; 5: 27.
6. Sposoby otsenki gigenicheskogo sostoyaniya polosti rta [http:// www.plaintest.com/stomatology/hygiene-choice/estimation](http://www.plaintest.com/stomatology/hygiene-choice/estimation) Data obrashcheniya: 19.02.2019
7. Trezubov V.V. i dr. Indeksnyaya otsenka gigenicheskogo sostoyaniya zubnykh protezov i apparatov razlichnykh konstruktsii. Institut stomatologii. 2010; 49(9): 46-7.